

OBTAINING HIGH-QUALITY CALCIUM AND MAGNESIUM-CONTAINING PHOSPHORIC FERTILIZERS BASED ON PURIFIED OF WET PROCESS PHOSPHORIC ACID

I. Shamshidinov¹, G. Kodirova², R. Najmiddinov³, L. Tursunov

Doctor of technical sciences, Professor of Namangan State Technical University¹

Doctor of Philosophy of Namangan State Technical University²

Doctor of Philosophy of Namangan State Technical University³

Doctoral student of Namangan State Technical University⁴

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Abstract. *The aim of the study is to reduce the content of fluorine and sulfates in extraction phosphoric acid by introducing calcium-containing raw materials into the finished extraction pulp before filtration and obtaining high-quality calcium and magnesium-containing phosphoric fertilizers based on it. The optimal technological parameters of the process of simultaneous defluorization and desulfurization of wet-process phosphoric acid (WPPA) from phosphorites of the Central Kyzylkum desert with calcium carbonate, dolomite and washed calcined phosphoconcentrate (WCPC) were found by introducing them into the second section of the extractor, into the finished extraction pulp in an amount of 100% for binding sulfates and 100-150% for binding of sulfates. Binding of fluorine, as well as obtaining high-quality products based on purified WPPA. The degree of transition of fluorine into the gas phase and phosphogypsum at a rate of 100-150% of calcium oxide for binding fluorine is 86.2-89.4% and its content in the extraction phosphoric acid decreases from 1.18% to 0.22-0.29%. At the same time, the SO₃ content in the acid decreases from 1.21% to 0.24-0.26%. The filtration rate of sulfate-phosphate pulp changes insignificantly and amounts to 807.6-812.6 kg/m²·h by dry residue.*

Keywords: *wet-process phosphoric acid, extraction pulp, calcium carbonate, washed burnt phosphate concentrate, defluorination, desulfurization, filtration, calcium and magnesium phosphates.*

Introduction. Fluoride compounds have the most harmful effects on the environment. Studies show that fluoride adversely affects not only plants, but also humans, animals, fish, causing various serious diseases [1, 2].

Some plants are ability of accumulating significant amounts of fluoride. So, tea contains from 57 to 1370 mg of fluorine per 1 kg, and in cotton - up to 4500 mg of fluorine per 1 kg [2]. Moreover, fluorine accumulates in cottonseeds, and in the producing of cottonseed oil production, passes into it. Studies show that when fluoride enters the soil, including with mineral fertilizers, the fluoride content in the crop increases [3]. The amount of fluoride absorbed by plants increases even more in the presence of nitrogen-phosphorus-potassium fertilizers [4].

The main source of fluoride entering the soil is phosphorus-containing fertilizers. Thus, apatites and phosphorites contain, on average, 3.0 and 2.7% fluorine, respectively. Extractive phosphoric acid (WPPA) produced based on phosphorites of Central Kyzylkum contains up to 1.5% fluorine. Methods of precipitation from acid with alkali metals in the form of silicofluorides are ineffective, since the acid practically does not contain acid-soluble silicon [5].

In the process of processing natural phosphates, the fluorine contained in them is redistributed between the gas, liquid (H_3PO_4) and solid (phosphogypsum) phases. When phosphoric acid is obtained accordingly by dihydrate scheme, 80-85% of the fluorine contained in the raw material (apatite and phosphorite) goes into acid and in the process of its further processing remains in fertilizers.

In connection with the ever-increasing consumption of fertilizers in agriculture, a significant increase in the production of phosphorus fertilizers, especially complex ones, the danger of a possible "fluoridation" of soils, plants and water basins becomes obvious [6]. The detrimental effect of fluorine compounds entering the atmosphere and groundwater on the animal and plant world has been studied quite fully [3, 4, 7]. To precipitate fluorine from extraction phosphoric acid in the form of poorly soluble compounds of alkali metal silicofluorides, sulfates, chlorides, phosphates, carbonates and sodium and potassium hydroxides are used [8]. These methods are based on the chemical interaction of the above salts with hydrofluorosilicic acid and its soluble salts present in WPPA. The degree of purification from fluorine reaches up to 90%. However, the degree of purification from fluorine WPPA from phosphorites of the Central Kyzylykum by this method does not exceed 38-40%.

The processes of purification of WPPA from phosphorites of the Central Kyzylykum with alkali metal salts are described in detail in the literature. In [9], WPPA was purified sequentially from sulfates and only then from fluorine. The authors studied in detail the processes of defluorination of WPPA based on phosphorites of the Central Kyzylykum with sulfate, dihydrogen phosphate, sodium metasilicate and showed the possibility of increasing the degree of defluorination from 38-40% to 80-85% by introducing acid-soluble silicon in the form of silicon dioxide and metasilicate and developed a technology for defluorination of WPPA [10-17].

There are materials on desulfurization of defluorinated WPPA with raw phosphate raw materials from the Central Kyzylykum [18], carbonate, calcium oxide, washed calcined phosphorite [19-23]. A patented method for purifying WPPA from fluorine and sulfate compounds to obtain fodder precipitate [24]. However, no materials have been found for the simultaneous purification of fluorine and sulfates from sulfuric-phosphoric acid extraction pulp while obtaining WPPA from Central Kyzylykum. The current demand for phosphate raw materials in the world is 190 million t. or 43 million t. per year on P_2O_5 . The demand for phosphate raw materials is projected to increase to 1.3 million t. by 2020 and to 2 million t. by 2030. By 2050, the demand for phosphate raw materials will increase to 220 million t. or up to 70 million tonnes P_2O_5 [25].

Due to the growing demand of agriculture for phosphorus fertilizers and a decrease in reserves of high-quality phosphate raw materials year after year, the attraction of low-grade phosphate raw materials for processing into phosphorus fertilizers is currently one of the urgent tasks. Neutralization of extraction phosphoric acid with natural carbonate raw materials makes it possible to increase the amount of output by 4-5% than when receiving ammophos. Produced phosphoric fertilizers contain a large amount of fluorine (up to 4%) and this, to a certain extent, has a negative effect on the agrochemical efficiency of fertilizers. In this regard, studies were carried out to purify WPPA from fluorine.

Fluorine decontamination of WPPA is carried out in three ways [8, 24]: acidic fluorination; transformation of fluorine compounds into acid insoluble compounds and extraction from WPPA; extraction of fluoride compounds from acid by organic reagents.

The treatment of WPPA by these methods requires additional reagents, heavy equipment and high capital costs. Therefore, research into both fluorine and sulphate purification methods for WPPA is relevant.

Methods and materials. Natural minerals were used for research: calcium carbonates - limestone, composition (wt.%): CaO = 54.09, MgO = 1.07, R₂O₃ = 0.19, SO₃ = 0.09, CO₂ = 43.65, H₂O = 0.29, insoluble residue = 0.62; dolomite composition (wt.%): CaO = 32.36; MgO = 18.68; CO₂ = 45.76; R₂O₃ = 0.53; H₂O = 1.0, insoluble residue = 1.34, washed and calcined phosphoconcentrate (WCPC) of Central Kyzylkum, composition in wt. %: P₂O₅ = 26.20; CO₂ = 3.08; CaO = 57.64; MgO = 0.60; R₂O₃ = 0.79; SO₃ = 2.22; F = 2.88; n.o. = 1.54 and WPPA, composition in mass. %: P₂O₅ = 17.23 and 20.15; CaO = 0.32 and 0.41; MgO = 0.66 0 0.82; Fe₂O₃ = 0.36 and 0.28; Al₂O₃ = 0.81 and 0.33; F = 1.18 and 1.32; SO₃ = 1.21 and 2.22.

The deposition of fluorine and sulfates from the extraction pulp was carried out with calcium carbonate (chalk) dolomite and WCPC at a rate of calcium oxide of 60-150% for the formation of calcium fluoride and 80-100% for the binding of SO₃.

Experiments were carried out on a laboratory, model continuous operation unit consisting of a two-sectional extractor made of a stainless steel EI-943 with an insulated electric heating layer, which is provided with electric mixers and acid and phosmoc dispensers. Capacity of equipment 150 g phosphate, working volume of extractor 2.5 l.

The decomposition of phosphorite was carried out with a mixture of sulfuric and recycled phosphoric acids in a dehydrate mode. The system worked without pulp circulation. Before starting work, both sections of the extractor were filled with extraction slurry, previously obtained under the conditions of a dihydrate regime from standard raw materials. The stirring speed in the first reactor was 120-140 rpm, and in the second 80-100 rpm, the process duration was 3 hours.

The ratio of liquid and solid phases is 2.5, the excess of sulfate ion in the liquid phase in terms of SO₃ was 3.3-3.5 g / 100 ml. Filtration was carried out on a Buchner funnel through a filter cloth at a vacuum of 400 mm Hg.

The residence time of the extraction slurry in the first section of the reactor is 1 hour, and in the second 2 hours, since the volume of the second reactor is 3 times greater than the first, and the rotation speed of the stirrer is 1.5 times less than in the first reactor. This provides favorable conditions for the crystal formation process.

Chemical analysis of raw materials, intermediate and final products was carried out according to known methods [26-29]. The results obtained are shown in Tables 1, 2, 3, 4 and figures 1, 2.

Results and discussion. Table 1 shows that when WPPA is obtained without the introduction of calcium carbonate, dolomite and WCPC, the degree of transition of fluorine to the gas phase is 5.1% of the total amount in phosphorite, 41.3% is transferred to phosphogypsum and 53.6% remains in the WPPA. When calcium carbonate or dolomite is added to the extraction slurry, the following reactions can occur:

Table 1

Influence of the rate of calcium carbonate on the chemical composition of WPPA and the distribution of fluorine by phases

The name of indicators	Total calcium carbonate rate for fluorine binding, % of stoichiometry						
	-	60	80	100	120	140	150
Standard calcium carbonate for binding free H ₂ SO ₄ , % of stoichiometry	-	80	100	100	100	100	100
Standard calcium carbonate for binding free H ₂ SO ₄ , % of stoichiometry							
P ₂ O ₅	17,23	17,28	17,25	17,19	17,10	16,98	16,90
CaO	0,32	0,39	0,54	0,88	1,40	2,21	2,73
MgO	0,66	0,72	0,71	0,68	0,68	0,67	0,67
SO ₃	1,21	0,47	0,28	0,26	0,25	0,25	0,24
R ₂ O ₃	1,17	1,09	1,08	1,08	1,07	1,08	1,07
F	1,18	0,62	0,46	0,29	0,24	0,23	0,22
suspensions	0,29	0,31	0,27	0,24	0,21	0,18	0,15
Fluorine transition degree,%							
In phosphogypsum	41,3	69,1	74,5	81,8	84,9	85,2	85,4
Into the gas phase	5,1	5,1	4,9	4,4	4,2	4,1	4,0
total	46,4	74,2	79,4	86,2	89,1	89,3	89,4

Table 2

Technological indicators for the production of defluorinated and defluorinated extraction phosphoric acid

The name of indicators	The total rate of calcium carbonate for the binding of fluorine and sulfates,% of stoichiometry						
	-	140	180	200	220	240	250
K _{decom.} %	99,1	99,0	98,9	98,9	98,9	98,8	98,8
K _{extractions} , %	96,3	96,2	96,2	96,1	96,1	96,1	96,1
K _{wash.} , %	99,0	99,1	99,1	99,2	99,2	99,2	99,2
K _{the output} , %	95,3	95,3	95,3	95,3	95,3	95,3	95,3
Pulp density (ρ), g/cm ³ at 25°C	1,24	1,24	1,24	1,24	1,25	1,25	1,25
Pulp viscosity (η), centipoise (cst) at 25°C	3,10	3,42	3,52	3,61	3,68	3,72	3,73
Filtration rate of the extraction pulp, kg/m ² ·h	815,4	812,6	811,7	810,6	809,5	808,3	807,6

Table 3

Influence of the WCPC rate on the chemical composition of WPPA and the distribution of fluorine by phases

The name of indicators	Phosphorite rate for fluorine binding,% of stoichiometry						
	-	60	80	100	120	140	150

Rate of washed fired fosconcentrate for free H ₂ SO ₄ binding,% of stoichiometry	-	80	100	100	100	100	100
Chemical composition of WPPA, wt. %							
P ₂ O ₅	20,15	20,87	21,28	21,13	21,71	21,81	21,89
CaO	0,41	1,04	1,17	1,26	1,55	1,94	2,15
MgO	0,82	0,85	0,86	0,85	0,88	0,89	0,88
SO ₃	2,22	0,90	0,61	0,47	0,48	0,48	0,48
R ₂ O ₃	0,61	0,63	0,64	0,63	0,65	0,66	0,66
F	1,32	0,74	0,56	0,36	0,30	0,31	0,31
suspensions	0,25	0,34	0,31	0,25	0,27	0,28	0,19
Degree of fluorine passage,%							
To phosphogypsum	41,3	69,1	74,5	81,8	84,9	85,2	85,4
To the gas phase	5,1	5,1	4,9	4,4	4,2	4,1	4,0
Total	46,4	74,2	79,4	86,2	89,1	89,3	89,4

Figure 1. Influence of the rate of calcium carbonate (1) and WCPC (2) on the degree of defluorination.

Figure 2. Influence of the rate of calcium carbonate (1) and WCPC (2) on the degree of desulfurization.

Magnesium fluoride, unlike calcium fluoride, is more soluble in acids, and reacts with strong acids, in particular sulfuric, to form magnesium sulfate and hydrogen fluoride by the reaction:

This process is complex, since monophosphate and magnesium sulfate, which are readily soluble in WPPA, can interact with calcium carbonate to form calcium sulfate and monophosphate. However, magnesium carbonate will immediately react with phosphoric acid to form magnesium monophosphate. This is confirmed by the fact that the magnesium content in WPPA almost does not change and remains at the level of 0.66-0.72% (table 1). With the introduction of calcium carbonate and the formation of calcium fluoride, the amount of fluorine released into the gas phase decreases from 5.1 to 4.0%, which indicates the release of its main amount at the beginning of the process in the first reactor. The total degree of transition of fluorine into the gas phase and phosphogypsum with the introduction of CaCO_3 during decomposition at a rate of 100-150% is 86.2-89.4%. The fluorine content in WPPA is 0.22-0.29%, which is 4.1-5.4 times less than in the case without the introduction of calcium carbonate.

The degree of defluorization of WPPA at a rate of 100-120% CaO in the form of CaCO_3 for fluorine content is 75.4-80.5%, and desulfurization is 78.5-79.3% at a rate of 100% (Figures 1 and 2). It can be seen from the figures that at a rate of calcium carbonate over 120%, based on the available content of fluorine and sulfates in the acid, the degrees of defluorination and desulfurization change insignificantly. The amount of fluorine remaining in the WPPA is 10.6-13.8% of the total amount in phosphorite. When the rate of calcium carbonate changes to the available fluorine in phosphorite from 60 to 100%, an additional transition of fluorine to phosphogypsum by 27.8-40.5% is observed. An increase in the rate of calcium carbonate to 120-150% increases the degree of transition of fluorine to the solid phase by only 3.1-3.6%.

The excess content of calcium carbonate during the precipitation of fluorine from WPPA is spent on the formation of calcium sulfate, with an excess of sulfuric acid, and monocalcium phosphate, by interaction with phosphoric acid. From the data in Table 1, it can be seen that the SO_3 content decreases from 1.21% to 0.24-0.26%, and the calcium oxide content increases from 0.32% to 2.73%. In this case, the coefficients of decomposition, recovery, washing and yield are 98.8-99.1%, 96.1-96.3%, 99.0-99.2% and 95.3%, respectively, for the norms of calcium carbonate at binding of fluorine from 60 to 150% and excess sulfuric acid from 80 to 100% (Table 2).

The filtration rate of phosphogypsum is relatively high and amounts to 807.6-812.6 kg / m² · h on dry matter basis.

Table 3 and Figures 1 and 2 show the results of defluorination and desulfurization of WPPA with washed fired fosconcentrate of Central Kyzylkum. In contrast to the use of calcium carbonate in the acid purification process, the use of WCPC increases the P_2O_5 content in the production WPPA from 19.85-20.15% to 20.15-21.89%, the CaO content in the acid is 1.46-2, 15% at a rate of 120-150% for the formation of calcium sulfate, the content of MgO and SO_3 is approximately the same, the content of fluorine is reduced in the acid to 0.31%. Figures 1 and 2 show comparative data on the degree of defluorination and desulfurization with calcium carbonate, dolomite and WCPC. The figures show that with the introduction of calcium carbonate, the degree of defluorination is higher by 2.4-2.7%, and the degree of desulfurization is worse by 1.7-2.3% at a rate of 100-120% CaO for defluorization and desulfurization.

When fluorine and sulfates are precipitated by dolomite raw materials at 100% CaO in relation to fluorine and 100% CaO in relation to sulfates, the SO₃ content in WPPA decreases by 0.39%, and F by 0.35%. When the stoichiometric ratio of dolomite to fluorine is increased to 120%, the SO₃ content of the product decreases to 0.26% and F is 0.24%.

With an increase in the norm of dolomite raw materials, a further decrease in the content of fluorine and sulfates does not occur.

After filtration of the extraction pulp, a purified solution of WPPA is formed, composition (wt.%): P₂O₅ = 17.38; CaO = 1.09; MgO = 1.07; SO₃ = 0.26.

After filtration of the extraction pulp using limestone, a purified EPA of the composition (wt%) is formed: P₂O₅ = 17.38; CaO = 1.19; MgO = 0.77; SO₃ = 0.26; F = 0.23.

The researches which carried out have shown the fundamental possibility of simultaneous defluorination and desulfurization of WPPA from phosphorites of Central Kyzylykum by introducing calcium carbonate and WCPC into the extraction pulp.

The optimal rate of calcium carbonate and WCPC are 100-120% CaO for the formation of calcium fluoride and 100% CaO for the formation of calcium sulfate. At the same time, the content of sulfates decreases from 1.21% to 0.24-0.26%, fluorine from 1.18% to 0.22-0.29%, the degree of transition of fluorine into the gas phase during extraction decreases from 5.1% up to 4.2-4.4%, and in phosphogypsum it increases from 41.3% to 81.8-84.9%. In order to obtain high-quality defluorinated phosphorus fertilizers containing calcium and magnesium phosphates, a two-stage process of neutralizing WPPA with natural calcium and calcium-magnesium carbonates (limestone, dolomite) has been studied.

The first stage was carried out in the process of obtaining purified extraction phosphoric acid by introducing calcium carbonate or dolomite in an amount of 100% CaO for fluorine precipitation and 120% CaO for SO₃ precipitation.

The second stage of neutralization was carried out with the stoichiometric norm of CaCO₃ (pH = 2.8-3.5), corresponding to neutralization of the purified WPPA to calcium monophosphate and magnesium monophosphate. The resulting pulp was evaporated to a content of 30-35% H₂O and dried at a temperature of 100-105°C. Technological indicators of the process of neutralizing WPPA with limestone and dolomite raw materials, the chemical compositions of the intermediate and final products obtained are shown in Table 4.

When neutralizing WPPA, purified from fluorine and sulfates, with limestone or dolomite at a stoichiometric rate, phosphate slurry is formed, with an SO₃ content of 0.24% and a content of 0.22 and 0.23% F, respectively (Table 4).

As a result of evaporation and drying of the suspension, fertilizers of the composition (wt.%): P₂O₅ (total) were obtained. = 51.99 and 49.84; P₂O₅ (ac.c.a.) = 50.83 and 48.97; P₂O₅ (w.s.) = 47.43 and 46.29; CaO = 12.96 and 19.85; MgO = 8.84 & 1.07; SO₃ = 0.74 and 0.70; F = 0.70 and 0.63; H₂O = 2.95 and 3.51. In this case, the ratio [P₂O₅ (ac.c.a.): P₂O₅ (total)] x100 is 97.77 and 98.25%, and the ratio [P₂O₅ (w.s.):P₂O₅ (total)] x100 is 91.22 and 92.88%.

The resulting fertilizers are high quality, environmentally efficient, such as double superphosphate type fertilizers. In fig. 3 shows a block diagram of material flows for the production of calcium and magnesium phosphate fertilizers.

Table 4

Technological indicators and chemical composition of products of neutralization of WPPA with limestone and dolomite raw materials

№	Indicators	Chemical composition, %			
		Superphosphate pulp		Finished product - calcium and magnesium phosphates	
1.	Stoichiometric norm of CaCO ₃ for CaO at the 1st and 2nd stages of the process,%: In the 1st stage on F In the 1st stage according to SO ₃ In the 2nd stage - to neutralize WPPA	100 100 100	120 100 100	100 100 100	120 100 100
Neutralization by dolomite					
2.	P ₂ O ₅ (total)	16,47	16,77	50,08	51,99
3.	P ₂ O ₅ (ac.c.a.)	15,72	16,40	47,75	50,83
4.	P ₂ O ₅ (w.s.)	14,78	15,32	44,86	47,43
5.	CaO (total)	4,36	4,18	13,25	12,96
6.	MgO (total)	2,84	2,85	8,64	8,84
7.	SO ₃ (total)	0,36	0,24	1,02	0,74
8.	F (total)	0,32	0,23	0,98	0,70
9.	H ₂ O	68,04	68,71	2,81	2,95
10.	(P₂O₅ ac.c.a.: P₂O₅ total) x100,%	95,45	97,79	95,35	97,77
11.	(P₂O₅ w.s.:P₂O₅ total.)x100, %	89,74	91,35	89,58	91,22
Neutralization by limestone					
12.	P ₂ O ₅ (total)	16,86	17,07	49,56	49,84
13.	P ₂ O ₅ (ac.c.a.)	16,30	16,78	47,90	48,97
14.	P ₂ O ₅ (w.s.)	15,38	15,90	45,11	46,29
15.	CaO (total)	6,84	6,80	20,10	19,85
16.	MgO (total)	0,33	0,37	0,98	1,07
17.	SO ₃ (total)	0,27	0,24	0,82	0,70
18.	F (total)	0,26	0,22	0,75	0,63
19.	H ₂ O	67,08	66,95	3,26	3,51
20.	(P₂O₅ ac.c.a.: P₂O₅ total) x100,%	96,68	98,30	96,65	98,25
21.	(P₂O₅ w.s.:P₂O₅ total.)x100, %	91,22	93,15	91,02	92,88

In this case, the ratio [P₂O₅ (ac.c.a.): P₂O₅ (total)] x100 is 97.77 and 98.25%, and the ratio [P₂O₅ (w.s.):P₂O₅ (total)] x100 is 91.22 and 92.88%.

The resulting fertilizers are high quality, environmentally efficient, such as double superphosphate type fertilizers.

In fig. 3 shows a block diagram of material flows for the production of calcium and magnesium phosphate fertilizers.

Figure 3. Flow chart of material flows for the production of calcium and magnesium phosphate fertilizers.

Conclusion. Thus, the studies carried out have shown the possibility of simultaneous defluorization and desulfurization of extraction phosphoric acid from phosphorites of the Central Kyzylkum by introducing a calcium-containing reagent into the finished sulfuric-phosphoric acid pulp in an amount of 100% from the reagent for sulfates and 120% based on fluorine. Neutralization of purified WPPA with dolomite at the rate of 70-100% for the formation of monocalcium and monomagnesium phosphates makes it possible to obtain defluorinated phosphorus fertilizers similar in composition to double superphosphate.

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